

La Sfera Challenge

Squadra Italia

Squadra Italia will transcribe the version found in the Vatican Library, Urb. Lat. 752, **ff. 3r-26v**

DUE TO THE POST-PANDEMIC RETURN TO WORK, *SQUADRA ITALIA* WILL NOT PARTICIPATE IN THE CHALLENGE. THEY WILL, HOWEVER, STILL CONTRIBUTE A TRANSCRIPTION. *GRAZIE, SQUADRA ITALIA!*

f. 25r

TEAM DOCUMENTS

Transcription Portal

Project Log

Rules and Guidelines

Team Updates:

Squadra Italia members include:

- Paola Manoni, Responsible for the Coordination of IT Services, Vatican Apostolic Library, Team Lead
 - Claudia Montuschi, Head of the Manuscripts Department of the Vatican Apostolic Library, Editor
 - Maria Gabriella Critelli
 - Elisabetta Caldelli
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